

Effectiveness of School's Feeding Program in Coping Pupils' Malnutrition on Their Academic Performance

Armel B. Bilbar, MAEd

Public School Teacher, DepEd-Bayawan City Division, Bayawan City, Negros Oriental Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

A School Feeding Program (SFP) is essential to provide a balanced diet to children which would in turn enable the children to increase their attention span hence better academic achievement. The School Feeding Program is a crucial component in the development of a holistic child (Adelman,2008).

Nutrition and health are powerful influences on a child's learning and how well a child performs in school. The effect of undernutrition on young children aged (0-8) can be devastating and enduring. In the area of cognitive development, "when there isn't enough food, the body has to make decision about how to invest the limited foodstuffs available. Good nutrition involves consumption of a variety of foods in appropriate amounts, since no single kind of food can provide all the necessary nutrients, protein, carbohydrates, fats, vitamins, minerals, fiber and water are all very important (Van Stuijvenberg, 2005).

Undernourished children have short attention span is linked to low glucose levels. Food provides a good amount of glucose among children, provision of balanced diet would enable children to develop their cognitive, psychomotor and affective domain. A healthy child will concentrate more in class work hence developing the cognitive part. He can also play to develop physically and will interact with others with a lot of ease and grow in self-esteem (Jukes, Drake and Bundy, 2008).

In addition to these programs, the month of July every year has been declared as the Nutrition Month to underscore the significance of good nutrition of school children. In short, government line agencies, like the Department of Health (DOH), the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), the Department of Education (DepEd), and the Local Governments (LGUs) are working hand in hand to put an end of the ailing condition of children contributed poor academic performance in school.

Just recently, the Department of Education (DepEd) has tried to institutionalize the School Feeding Program (SFP) in almost all schools across the country for the purpose of addressing malnutrition among school age children. It is also believed that through this program, dropout and failure rate will be minimized. The Department of Education recognizes the importance of good nutrition for the improvement of academic performance of learners. Hence, DepEd implemented a 2014 Budget for School-Based Feeding Program that catered the severely wasted school children in K to 12 nationwide.

Based on these conditions, the researcher is interested to find out the effectiveness of school's feeding program in coping pupils' malnutrition on their academic performance in Manduaw Elementary School, Bayawan City Division, Negros Oriental, hence, the conduct of this study.

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This is a descriptive research that utilized survey questionnaire. Descriptive research, according to Travers (2000), is used to describe the nature of a situation as it exists at the time of the study and explore the causes of particular phenomena.

This study is described the nature of the situations that exist in public school in Manduaw Elementary School, Bayawan City Division, Negros Oriental as to the effectiveness of school feeding program in coping malnutrition on pupils academic performance.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the pupils and teachers in Manduaw Elementary School, Bayawan City Division of Negros Oriental.

Research Instruments

This study utilized a standardized questionnaire to assess the effectiveness of schools' feeding program in coping malnutrition on pupils' academic performance. Part I is the socio-demographic profile consists of information of the pupils. Part II is the assessment of school feeding program.

Research Procedure

Upon the approval of the research, a letter of request is sent to the Dean of the Graduate Studies of Central Philippines State University asking permission to conduct the study for approval. The researcher sent another letter of request to the Division Superintendent thru the district supervisor to conduct the study for approval. Afterwards, a letter of the same purpose is sent to the school head asking permission to conduct the study as well as to get the secondary data of IP learners on the ECCD Checklist. After which, administering the survey questionnaire have followed accordingly to conduct the study. The data gathered were retrieved immediately, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted by the researcher.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents' Profile (N=108)

PROFILE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
SEX		
Male	53	49.1
Female	55	50.9
AGE		
5-6 years old	34	31.5
7-8 years old	25	23.1
9-10 years old	24	22.2
11-12 years old	25	23.1
PARENTS' EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT		
Elementary Level	38	35.2
Elementary Graduate	23	21.3
High School Level	40	37.0
High School Graduate	6	5.6
College Level		.9
FAMILY MONTHLY INCOME		
1000-3000	93	86.1
3001-6000	14	13.0
6001-9000	1	.9
INITIAL BMI		
13.5 below	83	76.9
13.5 up	25	23.5
RECENT BMI		
13.5 below	58	53.7
13.5 up	50	46.3
Total	108	100.0

Table 1 reveals that female obtains the highest frequency of 55 or 50.9 percent while the male has the frequency of 53 Or 49.1 percent.

This implies that most of the pupils at Basay and Manduaw Elementary Schools are females with the highest percentage result.

As to age, result reveals that 5 to 6 years old has the highest percentage of 31.5. These are followed by ages 7 to 8 years old and 11 to 12 years old with the same percentage of 23.1. Age of 9 to 10 years old gets the lowest percentage of 22.2 percent. The frequencies of their ages are 34, 25, and 24 respectively. It implies that 5 to 6 years old has the highest percentage among the ages of the pupils.

Furthermore, on Parents' Educational Attainment, result reveals that High School level gets the highest frequency of 40 and with the percentage of 37.0 of the respondents. This is followed by elementary level with the frequency of 38 or 35.2 percent. Then, the elementary graduate gets the frequency of 23 and with the percentage of 21.3. Those who are in high school graduate obtain the frequency of 6 and with the

percentage of 5.6. The lowest in parents' educational attainment with the frequency of 1 and with the percentage of 0.9 are those with college level.

More so, the family monthly income that ranges from PhP 1000 to 3000 obtains the highest frequency of 93 and with the percentage of 86.1. Whereas, family income of more than PhP 4000 to 6000 has the frequency of 14 or 13.0 percent. Family income of PhP 7,000 to 10,000 has the lowest frequency of 1 or 0.9 percent.

This implies that most of the respondents' parents are very low wage earners with a monthly income ranging from PhP 1000-3000.

In addition, in terms of the Nutritional status, result reveals that Initial BMI of 13.5 below has the highest frequency of 83 and with the percentage of 76.9 and BMI of 13.5 up has the frequency of 25 and with the percentage of 23.5. On the recent nutritional status, the BMI of 13.5 below has the frequency 58 or 53.7 percent and the BMI 13.5 up has the frequency of 50 and has the percentage 46.3.

This implies that the nutritional status initial and recent BMI of 13.5 below is much higher compare to BMI 13.5 up.

Children from families with low socio-economic status are at a greater risk of hunger, homeless, sickness, physical and mental disabilities, violence, teen parenthood, family stress and educational failure. Students from low-socio economic background that encounter these environmental factors are four times more likely to have learning disabilities than students from high socio-economic background while a combination of these environmental factors accelerate academic success.

A student, who has not eaten for days and has clothes that do not fit, cannot maintain focus in a classroom. G.U. Anene (Anene, 2005) argues that students from high social economics status compared to students from low social economic status families are not provided the same tools as the students from wealthy families. They are entering schools already behind those not living in similar conditions.

It further reveals that most of the pupils in Manduaw Elementary School, Basay Elementary School, Bayawan City Division of Negros Oriental are females. It further shows that most of the respondents' age is 5 to 6 years old. Moreover, as to the family monthly income, parents of the respondents are very low wage earners with a monthly income ranging from PhP 1000-3000. Most of their parents' educational attainments are high school level. The nutritional status of BMI initial and recent is BMI 13.5 below.

The next table presents the effectiveness of school feeding program that includes Health Physical Facilities, Management of Funds, Staffing /Working Committee, Feeding Paraphernalia, Food Preparation, Health Knowledge, Community Linkages, Management & Supervision, weighted mean will be used.

The effectiveness of school feeding program that includes Health Physical Facilities, Management of Funds, Staffing /Working Committee, Feeding Paraphernalia, Food Preparation, Health Knowledge, Community Linkages, Management & Supervision.

Table 2. Effectiveness of School Feeding Program that includes Health Physical Facilities, Management of Funds, Staffing /Working Committee, Feeding Paraphernalia, Food Preparation, Health Knowledge, Community Linkages, Management & Supervision
(N=108)

EFFECTIVENESS OF FEEDING PROGRAM	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	INTERPRETATION
Health Physical Facilities	4.47	0.378	Outstanding
Management of Funds	4.04	0.619	Very Good
Staffing /Working Committee	4.04	0.689	Very Good
Feeding Paraphernalia	4.41	0.461	Outstanding
Food Preparation	4.25	0.537	Outstanding
Health Knowledge	4.38	0.540	Outstanding
Community Linkages	4.39	0.494	Outstanding
Management & Supervision	4.36	0.515	Outstanding

Table 2 shows the effectiveness of school feeding program that includes Health Physical Facilities, Feeding Paraphernalia, Food Preparation, Health Knowledge, Community Linkages, Management & Supervision. Specifically, as to the Health Physical Facilities, Management of Funds, Staffing/Working Committee, Feeding Paraphernalia, Food Preparation, Health Knowledge, Community Linkages, Management & Supervision have an interpretation of outstanding with the mean scores of 4.47, 4.41, 4.25, 4.38, 4.39 and 4.36 and have the standard deviation of 0.378, 0.461, 0.537, 0.540, 0.494 and 0.515 respectively.

Meanwhile, on the Management of Funds, Staffing /Working Committee have the interpretation of very good with the same mean scores of 4.04 and have the standard deviation 0.619 and 0.689.

Bundy et al. (2009) suggests that appropriately designed school feeding programs increase access to education and learning and improve children’s health and nutrition, especially when integrated into comprehensive school health and nutrition programs.

School feeding contributes to the education and well-being of children. A hungry child does not grow, cannot learn as well and faces many health risks in the future. School feeding can bring children into school and out of hunger. It is far more than food-giving. They are an investment in the world’s poorest children. They are an investment in our common future and global stability. School feeding can bring children into school and out of hunger. Strong partnerships can increase factors that pull children to school. It is a springboard for many positive outcomes for poor children and their families. School feeding programs engage parents and communities in the promotion of public health, education and the creation of an independent future. Few safety-net programs provide so many multi-sector benefits- education- gender equality, food security, poverty alleviation, nutrition and health-in one single intervention (WFP, 2016).

This means that the effectiveness of school feeding program the health physical facilities has the highest mean among of the variables and its extent of effectiveness is within the range of 95% to 100%.

Table 3. Academic Performance of the Pupils

	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	INTERPRETATION
PUPILS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE	79.10	2.242	Fairly satisfactory

Table 3 reveals that the academic performance of the pupils has a grand mean of 79.10 and a standard deviation of 2.242, which is interpreted as fairly satisfactory.

The interaction between nutrition and education can be generally understood in three ways (Kazianga, de Walque et al. 2009). First, nutrition and health statuses influence the child's learning and his/her performance in school. That is poor nutrition among children affects their cognitive function and hence reduces their ability to participate in learning activities at school. Second, children who are malnourished or who are unhealthy are unable to attend school regularly and which in turn leads to poor academic performances. Third, hungry children encounter difficulties to concentrate and perform complex tasks than well nourished ones. This means that the pupils' academic performance is fairly satisfactory and teachers are always observe their performances.

Table 4. Relationship between the Profile of the Socio-Demographic Profile Respondents and the Pupils' Academic Performance

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS	ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE			
	R	P(r)	Decision	Interpretation
AGE	.070	.474	Retain H ₀	NS
SEX	-.159	.101	Retain H ₀	NS
PARENT EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	.009	.923	Retain H ₀	NS
FAMILY INCOME	-.040	.684	Retain H ₀	NS
NUTRITIONAL STATUS INITIAL BMI	.093	.338	Retain H ₀	NS
NUTRITIONAL STATUS RECENT BMI	.124	.201	Retain H ₀	NS

Sig. - Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.05

Not. Sig. – Not Significant if p-value is greater than 0.05

Table 4 presents the significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents such as age, sex, family income, parent educational attainment and nutritional status and the pupils' academic performance Pearson –r was used.

The relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents such as age, sex, family income, parent educational attainment and nutritional status and the pupils' academic performance.

Table 4 reveals that the age, sex, family income, parent educational attainment and nutritional status have no significant relationship to the academic performance because the p-value is greater than 0.05. This leads to accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant relationship between socio-demographic profiles of the respondents and the pupils' academic performance.

The result of the study is congruent to the result of Nasir (2012) that there are some factors of socio-demographic profiles that are not correlated to the students' academic performance.

This leads to accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant relationship between socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the pupils' academic performance.

Table 5. Relationship between the Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents and the Effectiveness School's Feeding Program

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE		Health Physical Facilities	Management of Funds	Staffing /Working Committee	Feeding Parapher nalia	Food Preparat ion	Health Knowledge	Community Linkages	Mngt Supervi- sion
AGE	Pearson Correlation	.096	-.010	-.041	-.097	.015	-.065	.017	.023
	p - value	.321	.918	.670	.317	.878	.506	.862	.811
SEX	Pearson Correlation	-.156	-.047	-.111	-.181	-.074	-.108	-.122	-.229
	p - value	.108	.629	.251	.061	.449	.264	.208	.017
Parent Educ'la ttnmt	Pearson Correlation	-.162	-.081	-.037	-.014	-.050	.062	-.016	.004
	p - value	.093	.405	.704	.889	.610	.521	.866	.968
Income	Pearson Correlation	-.135	.041	-.050	-.081	-.008	.079	-.124	-.164
	p - value	.163	.674	.609	.407	.937	.415	.202	.090
NSIB	Pearson Correlation	-.176	.104	-.058	-.200*	-.079	-.005	.000	-.023
	p - value	.068	.284	.549	.038	.417	.958	.998	.815
NSRB	Pearson Correlation	.179	.043	.009	-.147	-.110	.043	-.124	-.201*
	p - value	.063	.656	.924	.130	.258	.657	.200	.037

Table 5 presents the significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness school's feeding program Pearson-r was used.

Significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness school's feeding program.

Table 6 result reveals that the relationship between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness school's feeding program have highly significant relationship on the nutritional status in initial BMI with the r of $-.200^*$ and p-value of 0.38 as well as on the nutritional status in Recent BMI with r of $-.201^*$ of .037 has highly significant relationship results.

This leads to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is highly significant relationship between socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness school's feeding program.

The result of the study is similarly explain to the result of Bittenheim (2012) that the nutritional status of children has significant relationship of feeding program by providing them enough nutritious food, calories and nutrients. Broca and Stamoulis (2003) that the Body Mass Index (BMI) have significant impact on the individuals productivity.

Some of the demographic factors of the pupils have no significant relationship as to the effectiveness of feeding program. According to Kie (1990) other factors of demographic variables had no effect of feeding on child's development. This leads to retain the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant relationship between socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness school's feeding program.

Table 6 presents the significant relationship between the effectiveness school's feeding program and the pupil's academic performance Pearson-r will be used.

Relationship between the Effectiveness of School's Feeding Program and the Pupil's Academic Performance

	School Feeding Program	Academic Performance
Health Physical Facilities	Pearson Correlation	.025
	p-value	.794
Management of Funds	Pearson Correlation	-.058
	p-value	.552
Staffing /Working Committee	Pearson Correlation	-.186
	p-value	.053
Feeding Paraphernalia	Pearson Correlation	-.065
	p-value	.501
Food Preparation	Pearson Correlation	-.055
	p-value	.569
Health Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	-.096
	p-value	.325
Community Linkages	Pearson Correlation	-.165
	p-value	.087
Management & Supervision	Pearson Correlation	-.138
	p-value	.154

Table 7 shows the relationship between feeding program that consists of Health Physical Facilities, Management of Funds, Staffing /Working Committee, Feeding Paraphernalia, Food Preparation, Health Knowledge, Community Linkages, Management & Supervision have no significant relationship on the pupils' academic performance.

This leads to retain the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant relationship between school's feeding program and pupils' academic performance.

The result of the study is congruent to the result of Naidu (2013) that the factors are not associated between each variables and it was stated that the lack of supports, poor health and malnutrition is a large contributor of low academic performance.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In light to these findings, the researcher concluded that the pupils' socio-demographic profile have no significant relationship to the academic performance. This leads to accept the null hypothesis and concluded that there is no significant relationship between socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the pupils' academic performance.

It is likewise concluded that the relationship between the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness school's feeding program have highly significant relationship on the nutritional status in initial BMI as well as on the nutritional status in Recent BMI. This leads to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is highly significant relationship between socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the effectiveness school's feeding program.

It is further concluded that the relationship between school's feeding program have no significant relationship on the pupils' academic performance. This leads to retain the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant relationship between school's feeding program and pupils' academic performance.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings and conclusions, the researcher formulates the following recommendations:

1. Improve some of the schools' learning environment to extent like the school clinics and canteens in support to improving the basic school services.
2. Provide pupils with sufficient learning health modules and software in order to improve the teaching-learning process, specifically about nutrition and health education.
3. Sustain implementation of the nutrition and health education intervention program, specifically the school-based feeding program for it has created a greater impact in the lives of pupils, thereby, reducing malnutrition rate of pupils and improving their academic performance.

4. The teachers need to be warm, supportive and nurturing towards learners who are psychologically unstable due to poor nutrition so as to raise their self-confidence, self-direction and self-esteem.
5. Relevant trainings relative to nutrition and health education will be provided to school heads to equip them with the needed technical knowledge.
6. Conduct further research related on the topic to amplify the finding of the study so that the generalization of wider scope and application can be formulated.

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APPENDICES

Questionnaire

Part II. Direction: Please **assess the extent of effectiveness of your feeding program by putting a check mark (/) on the box provided using the rating scale below.**

Verbal Description	Description	Weight
Outstanding	When the extent of effectiveness is within the range of 95% to 100%	5
Very Good	When the extent of effectiveness is within the range of 90% to 94%	4
Good	When the extent of effectiveness is within the range of 85% to 89%	3
Fair	When the extent of effectiveness is within the range of 80% to 84%	2
Poor	When the extent of effectiveness is within the range of 75% to 79%	1

A. Extent of the Feeding Program in School	O	V	S	F	P
	5	4	3	2	1

1. Physical Facilities

- 1.1 Neatness and orderliness of the School feeding center
- 1.2 Cleanliness of the lavatory used in washing all dishes after each feeding session
- 1.3 Functionality of handwashing and Toothbrushing area
- 1.4 Availability of a potable water supply
- 1.5 Availability of a storage room for Perishable & non-perishable goods
- 1.6 Functionality of a waste disposal System, zero waste management

	O	VS	S	F	P
	5	4	3	2	1
2. Management of Funds					
2.1 System of daily recording of all Purchased items evident					
2.2 Promptness in the liquidation of Financial reports					
2.3 Regular basis of updating records by the school BAC					
2.4 Transparency of financial report available in school Bulletin Board					
2.5 Updating of daily disbursement of SBFP funds by the head of school to the SBFP finance officer kept tracked					
3. Staffing/Working Committees(TWG)					
3.1 Roles, duties, and functions of school BAC delineated					
3.2 Roles, duties and functions of all working committees delineated					
3.3 Degree of parents' participation of the feeding program of the school, such as: marketing, cooking & serving					
4. Feeding Paraphernalia					
4.1 Availability of plates, bowls and glasses for use					
4.2 Availability of spoons and forks for use					
4.3 Availability of frying pans, kettles & casserole					
4.4 Availability of chopping board, shredders, peelers & knives					
B. Food Preparation & Distribution					
	O	VS	S	F	P
	5	4	3	2	1
5. Food Preparation & Distribution					
5.1 The (20) cycle menu preparation as Prescribed is planned.					
5.2 Preparation of vegetables & other raw food for cooking observed.					
5.3 System in food distribution to Pupils observed.					
5.4 Necessary gears during feeding Sessions utilized.					
5.5 Raw food items or ingredients to be cooked are carefully washed					
5.6 The (20) feeding days are followed					
6. Health Knowledge of Children					
6.1 Children observe handwashing procedure					
6.2 Concepts of good nutrition have been oriented to the children before eating					
6.3 Experiences relative to cooking, washing utensils & equipment and storing them in their proper places learned.					

O	VS	S	F	P
5	4	3	2	1

7. Community Linkages

- 7.1 Linkages with the Barangay Community Health workers established.
- 7.2 Linkages with the Municipal RHU office for technical support Established.
- 7.3 Support from other community Stakeholders drawn.

8. Management and supervision

- 8.1 Feeding program of the school in SIP & AIP incorporated.
 - 8.2 Nutritional Status Baseline for early identification of recipients For the feeding program Accomplished.
 - 8.3 Advocacy on the feeding program of the school to stakeholders conducted.
 - 8.4 Over-all implementation of the feeding program of the school supervised.
 - 8.5 Terminal reports on the progress implementation accomplished and ss submitted to the Division Office on time.
 - 8.6 Liquidation of funds utilized for the feeding program implementation accomplished and done on time.
-